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Curriculum Analysis: The State of Ethics in Computer Science Curriculum in Kenyan Universities.

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Abstract - In many developing countries', computing education curricula has not evolved in tandem with the needs and emerging issues of modern computing. Ethical and moral issues in the use of AI and data analytics on the rise, indicate a lack of ethical literacy and foundational ethical instruction among computer science practitioners. The current computing curriculum heavily emphasizes on hard computing skills while largely ignoring the inclusion of computing soft skills such as ethical decision making. In this study, an in-depth review of computing courses offered in 78 universities in Kenya was conducted. The analysis results reveal a significant gap of ethical aspect all computing courses across the universities. This paper makes recommendations for the next steps that can be taken to integrate ethics into computer science university curricula in developing countries.

Keywords – ChatGPT, Computer Science, Curriculum, Emerging Issues, Ethics

1. Introduction

Proliferation of computing technologies has turned data into one of the most valuable assets any organization can have. According to the World Economic Forum, increased amount of personal data “is generating a new wave of opportunity for economic and societal value creation.[1]. The rate at which we generate data is increasing at a dizzying pace, with estimates of 463 exabytes of data being created each day by 2025.

This vast amount of data has proven useful for various use cases in the business world, not limited to fraud detection; optimizing marketing campaigns; sports results prediction; political opinion and outcomes forecasting, targeting and product recommendations; stock market behavior forecasting; customer demand prediction and anticipating operational maintenance schedules. However, while still having all these benefits, there has been a global surge of unethical AI and data analytics activities in business practices. Reports indicate that many AI and data analytics practitioners are slowly turning into white collar criminals by using data analytics and AI in various unethical practices such as; manipulating consumers through microtargeting, swaying voters during elections and hiring tools that discriminates women. [2,3,4,5,6,7]

Most often than not, these unscrupulous activities go unnoticed to the untrained eye hence contravening moral agency. In essence, AI and analytics technologies are not ethically neutral and reflect the values that we ‘bake in’ to them with our design choices, as well as the values which guide our distribution and use. Wainwright asserted this by highlighting that the unintended side effect of AI and data

analytics activities, affects the lives of all stakeholders financially, socially and politically, irrespective of their awareness, both in the immediate and in the long run. Whilst these unethical escalate both locally and globally, there has also been surge in public awareness of ethical matters. However, it is unfortunate that there has not been a comparable increase in the number of university courses equipping upcoming AI and data practitioners with relevant competency to mud the murky ethical waters in the developing countries. [8,9]

The current computing curriculum offered by Commission for University Education in Kenya bundles up ethics with philosophy as an arts and humanities related course rather than a major part of the computer science curriculum. Without overruling the fact that there might be individual AI and data ethical related pedagogical practices in computer science education, the wider curricula outline does not give much weigh to ethical content as part of the skills students should gain from a CS course. With these glaring instructions gap, students therefore develop a mindset of “I’m just an engineer” or “it’s not my job to think about ethics” and eventually assume or overlook the moral responsibility of what they build or even pass it to someone else.[10]

Using qualitative and quantitative analysis, we reviewed 78 universities in Kenya and a total of 82 CS courses to present an overview of the CS curriculum in the Kenyan University based on the latest list of approved courses by Commission for University Education. This paper analyses the average percentage of ethics content in the CS programmes and gives an overview of the

pedagogical content for the identified ethics unit. The rest of the paper is organized as follows; background and related works; the dataset used and analysis done; findings and lastly a discussion of findings, recommendations and conclusions.

2. The Role of Ethics in Computer Science

2.1. Defining Ethics

Ethics, is defined by The English Oxford Living Dictionaries as a moral principle that governs a person's behavior or the manner in which they should conduct themselves undertaking an activity. In the data and AI context, Floridi & Taddeo defines ethics as all activities that evaluate moral problems related to data generation, curation, sharing and use, algorithms and corresponding practices in order to formulate and support morally good solutions. Further, we can classify ethical issues within the data and AI/ML context, into four major categories: *Privacy* - Who should control access to data about you; *Identity* - Is offline existence identical to online existence; *Ownership* - What does it mean to own data about ourselves; and *Reputation* - How can we determine what is trustworthy.[11]

These four tenets are the basis of the growing consensus for the need of ethical education among AI and data Analytics practitioners. The pervasive nature of how technology is deeply transforming the fabric of our society raises an alarm as well as reveals and shapes what human beings value and what we think is 'good' in life and worth seeking in the modern society. Technology is shaping how and why human beings seek good life and with what degree. Although, AI and big data analytics technologies are ethically neutral, they contribute a lot into how we are consolidating our moral and ethical perspectives in search of good life. How we implement AI algorithms and make use of big data analytics to create solutions matters. The "how" is not ethically neutral.

2.2. The Role of Ethics in Computer Science

Discussions of the role of ethics in Computer Science (CS) education also go back as far as 1991, where the ACM/IEEE Computer Society developed a Computing Curriculum. This curriculum states that "*Undergraduate programs should provide an environment in which students are exposed to the ethical and societal issues associated with the computing field. This includes maintaining currency with recent technological and theoretical developments, upholding general professional standards, and developing an awareness of one's own strengths and limitations as well as those of the discipline itself*". [12]

Unfortunately, this consensus, has not lived to achieve its intended purpose since most of the computing instructors at the time felt that ethics wasn't for computing student to

worry about; leave that to the philosophers. These attitudes have shifted favorably since then. Both computing instructors and data stakeholders have seen the need to develop a broader and better understanding of AI and data ethics, especially among those who design and implement data tools and practices, to meet the goal of beneficial data innovation and practice. Moral agency is taking a center stage in computing practices and becoming everyone's responsibility. Fiesler emphasizes that "*If anyone works in tech and they are not thinking about ethics, then such a practitioner is bad at their job*".[13]

2.3. Delivering Ethics in Computer Science Curriculum

Several approaches on how to deliver ethics within computer science curriculum have been proposed including implementing a tenth strand in the computer Science curriculum; Hiring a tutor who does "ethics"; developing a course dedicated to computer ethics and social impact. [14,15,16] Integrating ethics and social impact into existing courses, ethics and social impact in a capstone course and student developed ethical framework and usage policies. It is worth to note that these approaches are narrowly focused in that moral disposition in ethics instruction does not often translate into ethical experiences outside the classroom. Similar to the Kenya CS curricula approach, a tutor does not have any way to measure or prove that a CS student will be ethical in future at work.

The business world has also been vocal to further establish and implement different approaches that can help curb moral and ethical issues. Some of the frameworks and guidelines that have been developed include; Ethical Framework for Designing Autonomous Intelligent Systems. An Information Ethics Framework Based on ICT Platforms. The Ethics of AI Ethics: An Evaluation of Guidelines and a multitude of others have also been reviewed. [17,18] Although robust, all these guidelines majorly take an organizational perspective as opposed to focusing on a student perspective on dealing with the core instructional foundation of ethics in a classroom context.

The world's largest technical professional organization, IEEE (Institute for Electrical and Electronics Engineers), has also taken initiatives to bring help into the situation by establishing an entire division, devoted just to technology ethics. [19,20] In 2014, IEEE began holding its own international conferences on ethics in engineering, science, and technology practice to supplement its overarching professional code of ethics. Additionally, IEEE is also working on new ethical standards in emerging areas such as AI, robotics, and data management. Curriculum analysis unpacks a syllabus into its component parts; evaluates how the parts fit together; checks underlying beliefs and assumptions; and seeks justification for curriculum choices and assumptions. Although Kenya Institute of Curriculum Development (KICD) has been making steps in equipping

20 million Kenyans with relevant digital skills to enable citizens operate effectively under the digital economy, this critical issue is not captured in the just launched Public Schools Coding and Computer Programming Curriculum. [21] This paper analyzed over 50 CS syllabi content which clearly shows a glaring lack in ethics content and the need to integrate ethical content into the CS curricula. We envision that, just like doctors and lawyer would do, AI and Data practitioners will need to contribute various sorts of ‘goods’ to the public sphere by taking personal responsibility.

3. Materials and Methods

3.1 Data Set and Analysis

We curated a list of approved Computer Science courses in Kenya from the Commission for University Education (CUE) website page using a python Web Scrapping algorithm and then converted it into an Excel document found here - <https://bit.ly/3Fu8h95>. (This is a live document which I will maintain and as I continue to collaborate with stakeholders to create the most comprehensive view of this matter). Using ChatGPT, we then grabbed the list of all associated departments, program names with a web link where applicable and code, program units and unit codes for each university, in some instances I had to key them manually using publicly available information on Google.

This list is not exhaustive, and will be open for additions upon request. In this scope I have left out programmes titled “Information Technology” and only worked with a total of 78 Universities offering 82 “Computer Science” programmes. The current list has 1,256 Computer Science units offered across 15 universities that had their unit’s information accessible online. To describe the overall picture of the CS education in Kenya, I used the 82 Computer science programmes across all levels of study to:

- List all the units in each program;
- Identify all ethics/philosophy units offered in each program.

4. Results and Discussion

Out of the identified 82 computer programmes, 1,256 computer science units offered in the across 78 universities, only 12 units targeted ethics, philosophy or legal themes around technology representing a minuscule 0.009%. The analysis also revealed that ethics classes are not based within the Computer Science department. This indicates disciplinary breakdown by the programme department of the CS Unit, the instructor, and discipline of the instructor’s terminal degree(s) most of whom might a lack of technological context in their course materials. Although we did not have metadata for instructors, the unit codes indicated that ethical units are based on other departments.

Fig. 1 Total number of ethics units identified

The ethics units identified are predominantly offered in the undergraduate level of study. Most of them being offered in the third or fourth year of the programmes study. This could indicate the lack of academic weight being assigned to this theme as an area of study. We only had one instance of offering each in Masters and PhD Levels.

Fig. 2 Distribution of Ethics Units by year of study

The legal aspect of computing inclines to the understanding of law and issues in areas such as privacy, encryption, freedom of speech, copyrights and patents, computer crime, and computer/software reliability and safety under the Kenyan legal system. Additionally, Christian Ethics explore the major sources, methods, and insights of Christian social and theological ethics. These units therefore do not cover much around understanding of philosophical perspectives such as utilitarianism versus deontological ethics, moral responsibility and moral judgments in the context of technology.

The new landscape of the AI data and general computing industry presents the computing curricula with a new problem on how to address problems of the new millennium like ethics while providing both students and educational institutions a greater range of professional possibilities. The evolution of technologies being powered by data will continuously experience rapid changes for the foreseeable

future. This therefore means that curricula must continuously evolve to prepare students for lifelong learning and must include professional practice (e.g., communication skills, teamwork, ethics) as components of the programmes experience. This is not the current case from our results analysis in Kenya. There is scanty, if any emphasis on ethics as a pedagogical skill in computer science.

Computing faculty who are unfamiliar with the content and/or pedagogy of applied ethics should take initiatives advantage of the upskilling from the widely available tech ethical materials being published in journals. The overall goal for these members of faculty should be to equip computing professionals with better decision-making skills regarding their ethical, professional and social conduct. Although we have not been able to audit the course content in this scope, any student who graduates from a computer science program should be able to formulate and defend a position on an ethical question related to technology; describe the main ethical challenges posed by technology; analyze a proposed course of action in the context of various cultures, communities, and countries; apply relevant ethical theories, laws, regulations, and policies to decision making to support organizational compliance; and be able to recognize business needs, social responsibilities, and cultural differences of ethical decision, while applying relevant decision-making framework to analyze risks and decision alternatives at different business levels.

While a computer science student must first learn how to integrate theory and practice, to recognize the importance of abstraction, and to appreciate the value of good engineering design computer, they too need to appreciate their social ethical and professional responsibility early in their career.

From our results, the Kenyan Curricula seems to may have opted to deliver ethics as either an elective material or as a stand-alone course, integrated into traditional technical and theoretical courses. However, if ethical and social considerations are covered only in the standalone course and not “in context,” it will reinforce the false notion that technical processes are void of these other relevant issues. Because of this broad relevance, it is important that the core computer science courses integrate case studies that analyse the ethical, legal, social and professional considerations in the context of the technical subject matter of the course

6. Conclusion

Due to time limitation, I was not able to get the topics taught in each ethics unit, the literary works or specific tutors who teach CS related courses in the listed universities. However, the results of this study emphasize the need for all faculty members and instructors delivering computer Science content at all educational levels in Kenya to include ethics as part of their class, as well as computing programs with a goal towards increasing the reach of ethics across a curriculum. As Fiesler describes it, the students that we teach to code today will be the ones working at all levels in the tech companies that might—or hopefully might not—be involved in the ethics scandals of tomorrow. I believe this work forms the first of many steps towards standardizing and rigorously evaluating the content and effectiveness of specific types of ethics pedagogy in computer science being applied in Kenya.[13]

Conflicts of Interest

The author declares that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

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